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Abstract	This Data Management Plan (DMP) describes the management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed, and generated by the INGENIOUS project. This document also includes information on the data format, dissemination, and preservation plans in line with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) Data Management Protocols.
Keywords	data management

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Nature of the deliverable:		OTHER (ORDP: Open Research Data Pilot)
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web	✓
CL	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC	
CO	Confidential to iNGENIOUS project and Commission Services	

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
 DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
 DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.
 OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The iNGENIOUS project is a Horizon 2020 action providing open-access exportable data. This deliverable, the Data Management Plan (DMP), explains the project's action plan pertaining to data management; describing the main elements of the data management policy that has been used by iNGENIOUS project.

The topics that will be presented include:

- DMP structure;
- Data types and modes of preservation;
- Ethics to be followed;
- Intellectual Property Rights.

The DMP is an Open Research Data Pilot document that has been periodically updated from its creation to the end of the iNGENIOUS project.

OBJECTIVE OF THE DOCUMENT

The document covers the topics of exploitation of research data generated (and collected) within the project, and the dissemination of the public scientific results which are created by the project.

The scope of the current DMP is to make the iNGENIOUS public data easily:

- Discoverable;
- Accessible;
- Usable.

The document also covers data ethics and security for sensitive data, as well as project guidelines for intellectual properties.

STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

This document is divided into 4 sections. Section 1 provides the principle and structure of the management life-cycle of produced data, following FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) data management protocols. Sections 2 and 3 address data security/ethics, and intellectual property rights, respectively. Lastly, Section 4 outlines the detailed data management for each use case and proof of concept.

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ABBREVIATIONS

AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
API	Application Programming Interface
COM	COMmunication port
DBMS	Database Management System
DMP	Data Management Plan
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technologies
DLV	Data Virtualisation Layer
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPO	Data Protection Officer
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GPS	Global Positioning System
GMS	Google Mobile Services
IE	Innovation Elements
INGENIOUS	Next-GENeration IoT sOLutions for the Universal Supply chain
IoT	Internet of Things
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
M2M	Machine-to-Machine
MANO	Management and Orchestration
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
ML	Machine Learning
MMC	MultiMediaCard
MR	Mixed Reality
OTA	Over-The-Air
PoC	Proof of Concept
SD	Secure Digital
SD-MAC	Software-Defined Medium Access Control
SDN	Software-Defined Network
SD-PHY	Software-Defined PHYSical layer
SNR	Signal-to-Noise Ratio
UC	Use Case
WP	Work Package

1 DATA MANAGEMENT

Data management is an important component of the responsible conduct of any research initiative. Thus, there is a need to describe how data was collected, stored and preserved, as well as managed and shared. This document, which serves this purpose, is a Data Management Plan (DMP).

All Horizon 2020 projects are required to export open-access data, meaning end users should be able to have free-of-charge online access to project scientific information and outcomes. More specifically, the information that will be offered under the iNGENIOUS project includes:

- 1) peer-reviewed scientific research articles (published in scholarly journals);
- 2) research data (data underlying publications, curated data and/or raw data);
- 3) results to be incorporated into standards.

The iNGENIOUS DMP follows the template recommended by the European Commission [1]. The template includes the 4 guiding principles of FAIR data [2]:

<p>To Be Findable</p>	<p>F1. (meta)data are assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier F2. data are described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below) F3. metadata clearly and explicitly include the identifier of the data it describes F4. (meta)data are registered or indexed in a searchable resource</p>
<p>To Be Accessible</p>	<p>A1. (meta)data are retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol A1.1. the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable A1.2. the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary A2. metadata are accessible, even when the data are no longer available</p>
<p>To Be Interoperable</p>	<p>I1. (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation. I2. (meta)data use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles I3. (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data</p>
<p>To Be Reusable</p>	<p>R1. meta(data) are richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes R1.1. (meta)data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license R1.2. (meta)data are associated with detailed provenance R1.3. (meta)data meet domain-relevant community standards</p>

TABLE 1: GUIDING PRINCIPLES OF FAIR DATA [2]

1.1 FINDABLE DATA

The data generated in the framework of the iNGENIOUS project has unique identifiers so as to be easily discoverable by research communities. The identifier format is:

INGENIOUS_[Name]_[Type]_[Date]_[Owner]

where

- [Name] is a short and characteristic name for the data;
- [Type] is the type of data (code, publication, measured data);
- [Date] is the date when data was produced (format: DDMMYYYY);
- [Owner] is the owner (or owners) of the data (if exist);
- _ (underscore) is used as the separator between the fields;

For example, the following identifier:

INGENIOUS_PlatformConfiguration_code_23012021_NXW

indicates that the generated data is a code which is used to configure the platform. The configuration was completed on 23-01-2021 by NXW, which is the owner of the configuration.

In addition to the unique name identifier, the data set description is also important. The data set description is organized as metadata. Metadata is used to give information such which data are generated by the project and which are collected and used. The metadata identifier is formed in a similar way to the data identifier but with more details and, depending on the file format, will be either incorporated as a part of the file, in the Zenodo file description, or as a separate file e.x. text format.

The metadata identifier format is:

INGENIOUS_[Name]_[Type]_[Date]_[Owner]_METADATA

where

- [Name] is a short and characteristic name for the data
- [Type] is the type of data (code, publication, measured data)
- [Date] is the date when data was produced (format: DDMMYYYY)
- [Owner] is the owner (or owners) of the data (if exist)
- _ (underscore) is used as the separator between the fields

1.2 ACCESSIBLE DATA

The public access to the project data is ensured with the development of the project website, <https://ingenious-iot.eu>:

FIGURE 1: iNGENIOUS PUBLIC WEBSITE

The website permits easy and convenient access for users and research collaborators to the project's research data. Additionally, a Zenodo repository will be used for storing the project's public data. Zenodo is an open-access repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program. It allows for the dissemination of research papers, data sets, research software, reports, and any other research related digital artifacts [3]. The project has a Zenodo Community page, <https://zenodo.org/communities/ingenious-iot/> where the available is displayed and accessible:

FIGURE 2: iNGENIOUS ZENODOO COMMUNITY PAGE

A third source of public access is through the public repositories of individual partners:

UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA DE VALENCIA:
<https://riunet.upv.es/>

ⁱ Partner repositories will host those publications which are authored/co-authored by members of the hosting institution.

BARKHAUSEN INSTITUT GGMBH
<https://www.barkhauseninstitut.org/ergebnisse/publikationen>

TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET DRESDEN
<https://www.vodafone-chair.org/publications>

Available data and publications are linked through the project webpage in the following pages:

Project Deliverables:
<https://ingenious-iot.eu/web/deliverables/>

Open Access Data:
<https://ingenious-iot.eu/web/open-access-data/>

Open Source Code:
<https://ingenious-iot.eu/web/open-source/>

Scientific Publications:
<https://ingenious-iot.eu/web/publications-2/>

1.3 INTEROPERABLE DATA

Several data types, as detailed in Section 4, are foreseen to be generated within the project. In order to ease the procedure of data exchange the consortium partners will use a fully documented commentary on the data produced.

1.4 REUSABLE DATA

Public project data has been made open access. They are accessible through Zenodo repository, project website, and partner's open-access repositories, described above. The accessibility capability will be continued after the completion of the project through the Zenodo repository as well as the partner's open-access repositories.

For the data which cannot be openly shared, the reasons will be clearly stated and these data will be preserved in a repository in the project's Confluence site with limited access and not appear in the website of the project.

1.5 SUMMARY

A summary of the iNGENIOUS compliance with FAIR data management protocols is given in Table 2.

Principle	iNGENIOUS DMP
Findable Data	INGENIOUS_[Name]_[Type]_[Date]_[Owner] INGENIOUS_[Name]_[Type]_[Date]_[Owner]_METADATA
Accessible Data	website: https://ingenious-iot.eu Zenodo community: ingenious-iot Institutional repositories ⁱⁱ
Interoperable Data	fully documented commentary on the data produced
Reusable Data	Zenodo community: ingenious-iot (public access) iNGENIOUS Confluence site (restricted access) Institutional repositories ⁱⁱⁱ

TABLE 2: iNGENIOUS COMPLIANCE WITH THE FAIR PRINCIPLES.

ⁱⁱ Partner repositories will host those publications which are authored/co-authored by members of the hosting institution.

2 DATA ETHICS AND SECURITY

Details about data ethics and security including the project's DPO and GDPR compliance can be found in deliverable D7.4. As stated in D7.4, the iNGENIOUS project does not foresee the collection of any personal data on external users for any use case or proof of concepts. However, in case any data will be collected, it will be done in accordance with EU regulations and according to the minimisation principle in Article 5(1)(c) of the GDPR and Article 4(1)(c) of Regulation (EU) 2018/1725, which provide that personal data must be 'adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed'.

3 INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS

This section contains information regarding the management plan for Intellectual Property Rights or IPR(s). To this end, the IPR types, the IPR generation process and the management of background and foreground IPRs catalogue in iNGENIOUS project, in accordance with the H2020 Grant Agreement and project CA, is described.

IPRs include patents, patent applications and other statutory rights in inventions; copyrights (including without limitation copyrights in Software); registered design rights, applications for registered design rights, unregistered design rights and other statutory rights in designs; and other similar or equivalent forms of statutory protection, wherever in the world arising or available, but excluding rights in Confidential Information and/or trade secrets.

All the confidential data and IPR has been be stored in a secure centralized server repository, where partners shared technical documents and data obtained from the research and testing throughout the iNGENIOUS project. WP7 is tasked to ensure that the IPR and data management strategies are well defined and coherently executed while PMT will perform the monitoring of the IPR activities and IPR work. The activity of Innovation Elements (IE) generation that can lead to IPR(s) will be actively monitored in Task 7.2. A foreground catalogue will be kept to document relevant information of each determined IE, including:

- IE id
- IE description
- IE type
- Work item(s) where IE is generated
- Background IP elements by partner (BIP)
- Foreground IP element associated (FIP)
- Partners involved
- Patent(S)
- Ownership
- Access conditions

This catalogue will be accessible by partners in project's Task 7.2 Confluence pages. In addition, standardization and exploitation activities may include foreground IP elements that are contributing to each specific standardization activity and to each market opportunity, respectively. Therefore, the relevant foreground IP elements will also be documented within the standardization and exploitation catalogues in the respective Task 7.2 Confluence pages.

The mapping of IE to BIP, FIP, and Exploitable Elements (EEs) has been made public, with an interactive map available through the project website: <https://ingenious-iot.eu/web/innovation-and-exploitation-mapping/>

4 DETAILED DATA CATALOGUE

This section contains the data catalogue for each use case and proof of concept as a first step to ensuring the proper infrastructure is in place for compliance to the DMP. The data catalogue includes all data sets containing personal information, and in case personal data are involved, detailed information on the technical procedures for data collection, storage, protection, retention, and destruction. As the project progressed, the catalogue was updated to include any new handling of data within the project.

4.1 UC: Automated robots with heterogeneous networks (Industrial IoT)	
PoC: Tactile Internet and integration with IoT networks supporting Software Defined communications (SD-PHY, SD-MAC and SDN) and adaptive networking	
Type of data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Videos has been captured mainly to perform object detection at the MEC Sensor data has been collected and send to the control function Commands for steering the AGV and controlling the robot arm Status information has been delivered to the remote operators <ul style="list-style-type: none"> AGV location Environment status (temperature, pressure, humidity) Surveillance data to update virtual/real scene Network statistics (e.g., packet loss, SNR) Measurement data collected in trials
Data collection (methods, standards used)	Data collection has been performed by the involved IoT devices in the PoC, such as cameras, and environmental sensors. Localization information and statistical information has been collected from network functions. Some data has been generated from applications, such as control commands.
Documentation available	Most of the data format depends on the involved commercial devices that are documented by the manufacturers. Customized data format created within the use case has been gradually documented for internal use.
Storage and backup	Some of the data has been stored for a short term to perform offline performance analysis or to be used for ML training. No personal data has been stored.
Access and security	Network measurement data will be shared with partners in Work Package 3 and Work Package 4.
Ethical issues	None.
IPRs (data ownership, licensing, etc.)	None.
Planned use (documentation, validation, analytics, etc.)	Some data has been used used for research and analysis purposes within the period of the project.
Data sharing (public, partners only, selected personal, etc.)	Partners only. Video diffusion public
Preservation (delete-after-project, archive, etc.)	Delete-after-project. Video online public

TABLE 3: DATA CATALOGUE: AUTOMATED ROBOTS WITH HETEROGENEOUS NETWORKS (INDUSTRIAL IOT)

4.2 UC: Transportation Platform Health Monitoring	
Type of data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GPS Positioning Data (Railway Freight Carriages) • Speed Data (Railway Freight Carriages) • Loading Condition (Railway Freight Carriages) • Vibro-Acoustic Data – Wheels & Bearings
Data collection (methods, standards used)	Data collection is done by GMS connected edge devices and data edge loggers
Documentation available	Measurement data is stored binary or hex. COM data is TLS1.2 encrypted
Storage and backup	Data will be stored on MMC or SD card or transferred via TLS1.2 to partner middleware
Access and security	Data logging equipment and/or data will be provided to partners upon request
Ethical issues	None.
IPRs (data ownership, licensing, etc.)	The Data is Stakeholder specific and therefore not available for public use.
Planned use (documentation, validation, analytics, etc.)	The data will be used for iNGENIOUS research and analytic purposes.
Data sharing (public, partners only, selected personal, etc.)	Data logging equipment and/or data will be provided to partners upon request with confidentiality obligation.
Preservation (delete-after-project, archive, etc.)	Partners shall delete after iNGENIOUS project completion

TABLE 4: DATA CATALOGUE: TRANSPORTATION PLATFORM HEALTH MONITORING

4.3 UC: Situational Understanding and Predictive Models in Smart Logistics Scenarios	
Type of data	<p>Data related to operational processes carried out at the Port of Valencia and the Port of Livorno. The following data sets were considered and managed during the implementation and validation of the use case:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Port Call dataset: it includes vessels' arrival and departure information including departure/arrival times, berth terminals, vessels' identifiers, and vessels' characteristics. • Vessel Master dataset: historical dataset including detailed information of the characteristics of a large set of vessels performing container shipping activities. • Gate In and Gate out dataset: it includes time of arrival and departure of trucks and containers to/from the port. • Cargo Flow dataset: the relevant information used from this dataset is the container load and unload timestamps, the container number, the vessel's identifier, and the terminal name. • IoT Tracking dataset: it includes the data captured by the sensor installed on a truck (positioning, timestamps, temperature, humidity, etc.) • AIS dataset: dataset containing positioning data of the vessels along their trips together with vessels' metadata (e.g. identifier, size, etc.) <p>Further information about datasets is provided in the Deliverable D6.3 in which the data that has been used and how has been used is explained in detail.</p>
Data collection (methods, standards used)	<p>Data has been collected by FV and CNIT from the existing data sources available at the Port of Valencia (Valenciaport PCS, AIS, PI System OS/soft, etc.) and the Port of Livorno (TPCS, GTS3, AIS Dispatcher, M2M Platform, VBS, etc.).</p> <p>More precisely, the data collected from the Port of Valencia came from the following data sources:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Port Call dataset from the Port Community System (PCS) • Vessel Master dataset extracted from VESSL system (owned by FV) • Gate In and Gate out dataset from the PI System OS/soft • Cargo Flow dataset from the PCS • IoT Tracking dataset from the PostgreSQL of the demo • AIS dataset from the global VHF-based AIS system <p>Some of this data has been extracted and aggregated by DVL and then shared with Cross-DLT by using APIs for the distribution over different DLTs, according to their own capabilities. See section 4.6 for more details.</p>
Documentation available	<p>The description of all data streams involved in this use case is provided in deliverable D2.1. Some information is also public on https://www.valenciaportpcs.net/portcalls and https://tpcs.tpcs.eu/.</p>
Storage and backup	<p>Data has been stored in safe local and cloud database storage environments. Subsequently, a set of this data has been stored in Cross-DLT layer for enabling the exchange of data with different DLTs. See section 4.6 for more details.</p>
Access and security	<p>Data has been made accessible to partners involved in the development of this use case under specific agreements of confidentiality and non-disclosure between the owner of the data (Port of Valencia and Port of Livorno) and the recipient when specified. The data moved to Cross-DLT layer, data accessibility has been restricted to authorized users.</p>
Ethical issues	<p>Personal and sensitive data has been pseudoanonymised before sharing datasets following guidelines provided by GDPR and DPO (deliverable D7.4). See section 4.6 for more details.</p>
IPRs (data ownership, licensing, etc.)	<p>Data ownership resides in the entities providing the data, in this case both the Port of Valencia and Port of Livorno. External entities with access to these data will only exploit the data for project purposes related to this Use Case and exclusively during the lifetime of the project.</p>

Planned use (documentation, validation, analytics, etc.)	The aforementioned data sets will has been used as an input for developing Artificial Intelligence based algorithms in order to optimize Truck Turnaround Times in maritime ports and terminals.
Data sharing (public, partners only, selected personal, etc.)	Data has been made accessible to partners involved in the development of this use case under specific agreements of confidentiality and non-disclosure between the owner of the data (Port of Valencia and Port of Livorno) and the recipient, when considered private. The data moved to Cross-DLT layer, data accessibility will be restricted to authorized users.
Preservation (delete-after-project, archive, etc.)	Data will be deleted after the execution of the project and it will not be stored in any open-access repository during the project lifetime.

TABLE 5: DATA CATALOGUE: SITUATIONAL UNDERSTANDING AND PREDICTIVE MODELS IN SMART LOGISTICS SCENARIOS

4.4 UC/PoC: IMPROVE DRIVERS' SAFETY WITH MR AND HAPTIC SOLUTIONS	
Type of data	<p>Encoded, compressed and secured digital data transmission in a real-time application.</p> <p>Data involved,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · automatic guided vehicles (AGVs) presence (anonymized id & location) · IoT presence (anonymized id & location) · delivering goods (anonymized id & location) · transport routes, topography (secured) · over-the-air (OTA) wirelessly (secured) · over the network to the backhaul (secured) · cockpit 's cams, sensors, immersive gloves, trackbands and actuators (images, description - anonymized id & secured)
Data collection (methods, standards used)	<p>Data collection is mainly given by the IoT devices that are involved in the use case. The collection is made in real-time from e.g. cams and every time interval for e.g. available sensors and actuators (the broadcasting occurs upon actuation/triggering).</p> <p>The data is fetched from the futuristic immersive cockpit 's cameras and presence sensors that are installed in AGVs and its comprised immersive gloves, trackbands and actuators. This data is used only while the trial and final demonstration occurs and not stored thereafter, therefore will comply with the iNGENIOUS data management plan (DMP).</p>
Documentation available	<p>Documentation is not publicly available and instead will be shared only among the involved use case partners.</p> <p>The iNGENIOUS project describes the data format. The IoT platforms that are involved in the use case have proprietary data format but used for internal use only with no documentation publicly available.</p>
Storage and backup	<p>Other than non-personal data is temporarily stored locally and not backed up. It is merely used for the project trial and demonstration and though some data reaches up to the cloud this is in private mode and not open access (publicly available). Any historical data therefore is overridden periodically and erased after final demonstration.</p>
Access and security	<p>Will be performed through the iNGENIOUS DMP authentication & authorization methods</p>
Ethical issues	<p>None.</p> <p>No personal data will be collected specifically for the use case demo since own staff not external people will be used in principle.</p>
IPRs (data ownership, licensing, etc.)	<p>None.</p>
Planned use (documentation, validation, analytics, etc.)	<p>For the trial and final demonstration.</p>
Data sharing (public, partners only, selected personal, etc.)	<p>Partners only.</p>
Preservation (delete-after-project, archive, etc.)	<p>Delete-after-project.</p>

TABLE 6: DATA CATALOGUE: IMPROVE DRIVERS' SAFETY WITH MR AND HAPTIC SOLUTIONS

4.5 UC/PoC: Inter-modal Asset Tracking via IoT and Satellite	
Type of data	Data obtained by the IoT devices: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Real-time tracking of cargo especially relevant at the land and terminal sides (not so relevant at the seaside). Cargo conditions related to temperature and humidity. Safety conditions such as the container door opening.
Data collection (methods, standards used)	A Smart IoT Gateway collected and processed the data, sent by the IoT devices. The collection was made in real-time. The location, the humidity and the temperature of the cargo was updated every 5 minutes. The same for the door opening of the container. Furthermore, we used the Eclipse OM2M platform collects and stores raw data coming from the sensor installed on the iGENIOUS container.
Documentation available	All collected and processed data sets are described in <i>D6.2 – PoC Development, Platform and Test-bed Integration</i> and <i>D6.3 – Final Evaluation and Validation</i> . Additional technical documentation (e.g., user manual) is available from the vendors of the purchased IoT devices.
Storage and backup	Other than non-personal data is temporarily stored locally and not backed up. It is merely used for the project trial and demonstration and though some data reaches up to the cloud this is in private mode and not open access (publicly available). Any historical data therefore is overridden periodically and erased after final use case demonstration.
Access and security	Performed through the iGENIOUS DMP authentication & authorization methods.
Ethical issues	None. No personal data was collected specifically for the use case demo since own staff and not external people was used in principle.
IPRs (data ownership, licensing, etc.)	None.
Planned use (documentation, validation, analytics, etc.)	For the trial and final demonstration.
Data sharing (public, partners only, selected personal, etc.)	Partners only.
Preservation (delete-after-project, archive, etc.)	Delete-after-project.

TABLE 7: DATA CATALOGUE: INTER-MODAL ASSET TRACKING VIA IOT AND SATELLITE

4.6 UC (PoC): Supply Chain Ecosystem Integration	
Type of data	<p>The following data sets were considered and managed during the implementation and validation of the use case:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GateIn (Port of Livorno and Port of Valencia); • GateOut (Port of Livorno and Port of Valencia); • VesselArrival (Port of Livorno); • VesselDeparture (Port of Valencia); • Geolocation of vehicles (Port of Livorno); • Meteorological conditions (Port of Livorno); • Container door opening (Port of Valencia).
Data collection (methods, standards used)	<p>All data sets are collected from the underlying data sources and M2M platforms as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tuscan Port Community System: collects data related to GateIn, GateOut, VesselArrival and VesselDeparture in Livorno seaport; • PISystem M2M platform: collects and stores raw data related to GateIn and GateOut events in Valencia seaport; • Eclipse OM2M platform: collects and stores raw data coming from the sensor installed on the INGENIOUS container (door opening data); • Symphony M2M platform: collects and stores raw data coming from the IoT tracking device installed on a service vehicle in Livorno seaport; • Mobius OneM2M platform: collects and stores raw data coming from two meteorological stations in Livorno seaport. <p>The Data Virtualization Layer virtually aggregates all these data sets according to the scope of the use case and then allows third-party platforms/applications to consume them as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TrustOS: consumes GateIn, GateOut, VesselArrival, VesselDeparture and Door Opening data from the DVL; • Pseudonymization Function: consumes GateIn and GateOut data from the DVL and applies pseudonymization techniques to personal data; • Tracking Web Application: consumes geolocation data from the DVL in the port of Livorno.
Documentation available	<p>All collected and processed data sets are technically described in <i>D6.2 – PoC Development, Platform and Test-bed Integration</i> and <i>D5.3 – Final INGENIOUS data management platform</i>. Additional technical documentation (e.g., user manual) is available from the vendors of the purchased IoT devices such as the IoT tracking device used to track vehicles in seaport area (namely Mictrack MT821). The definition of the maritime events is based on the data models from the Tradelens Platform and therefore it is publicly available on https://platform-sandbox.tradelens.com/.</p>
Storage and backup	<p>Raw data are stored in the underlying M2M platforms. Additional storage (aggregated data) is also performed in the following components of the INGENIOUS Interoperability Layer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TrustOS: stores GateIn, GateOut, VesselArrival, VesselDeparture and Door Opening data. The storage is performed by using an internal database not accessible by external entities and it is used to guarantee a proper association between all DigitalAssets that have been created by the cross-DLT platform and the considered events; • Pseudonymization Function: stores GateIn and GateOut events from the Port of Livorno by using an encrypted database not accessible by external entities. This storage is used to keep track of the mapping between the original data sets and the pseudonymized ones. A retention time is also set to delete expired data sets; • Set of DLTs: each DLT stores only the Trustpoints related to a given maritime event from the TrustOS. Only TrustOS is able to check the metadata associated with the DigitalAssets that have been previously created.

<p>Access and security</p>	<p>All data sets are accessible only through RESTful interfaces, with an authentication procedure (e.g., JWT token) as well as through a VPN that guarantees the TCP/IP traffic encryption (e.g., TLS and SSL). This is applied to the following components of the iNGENIOUS Interoperability Layer:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DVL – TrustOS; • DVL – Pseudonymization Function; • TrustOS – DLTs; • DVL – M2M Platforms; • DVL – Tracking Web Application; • DVL – Awake.AI Platform; • TrustOS – DLT Event Visualizer. <p>Moreover, the access to the DVL's APIs, follows a role-based approach: data consumers (e.g., TrustOS, Pseudonymization Function, Tracking Web Application and Awake.AI Platform) are provided with only reading capabilities (ReadOnlyRole set in the Virtual Database) so that the existing information can not be neither accessible nor modified by third-party applications.</p>
<p>Ethical issues</p>	<p>The use case does not collect and/or process any sensitive data. Nevertheless, personal data are collected, processed and stored only in relation to the GateIn and GateOut events (trucks' plate number). To mitigate any ethical concerns arising from the use of such data, pseudonymisation techniques are applied accordingly. Moreover, in the case of data sharing with the partners of the iNGENIOUS consortium for analytics purposes, the NDA is also signed to guarantee a proper level of confidentiality.</p>
<p>IPRs (data ownership, licensing, etc.)</p>	<p>Data ownership resides in the entities providing the data, in this case both the Port of Valencia and the Port of Livorno. External entities with access to these data will only exploit the data for project purposes related to this use case and exclusively during the lifetime of the project.</p>
<p>Planned use (documentation, validation, analytics, etc.)</p>	<p>All data sets are part of the use case's scenarios and are used for the validation purposes as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GateIn: testing of the Pseudonymization Function and the interaction between TrustOS and the DLTs; • GateOut: testing of the Pseudonymization Function and the interaction between TrustOS and the DLTs; • VesselArrival: testing of the interaction between TrustOS and the DLTs; • VesselDeparture: testing of the interaction between TrustOS and the DLTs; • Geolocation of vehicles: testing of the integration between DVL and M2M platforms; • Meteorological conditions: testing of the integration between DVL and M2M platforms; • Container door opening: testing of the interaction between TrustOS and the DLTs as well as between the DVL and M2M platforms.

<p>Data sharing (public, partners only, selected personal, etc.)</p>	<p>Data are made accessible to partners involved in the development of the use case by means of agreements of confidentiality and non-disclosure with the data owners (Port of Valencia and Port of Livorno in this case). The following data sets are also made publicly accessible through a research data repository for the validation of results in scientific publications (in .json format):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Container door opening; • Geolocation of vehicles. <p>Such data sets refer to the measurement campaigns performed during the validation and demonstration of the use case:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Container door opening (on-filed measurement campaign conducted in November 2022 in the Port of Valencia with the door opening sensor installed on the iNGENIOUS smart container); • Geolocation of vehicles (on-filed measurement campaign conducted in February 2023 in the Port of Livorno with a service vehicle simulating a truck's run).
<p>Preservation (delete-after-project, archive, etc.)</p>	<p>Data will be deleted after the execution of the project and it will not be stored in any other public repository during the project lifetime.</p>

Commented [AT1]: Do we know where the open data will be stored?

TABLE 8: DATA CATALOGUE: SUPPLY CHAIN ECOSYSTEM INTEGRATION

5 CONCLUDING REMARKS

This deliverable, the iNGENIOUS Data Management Plan (DMP), has presented the project's action plan pertaining to the data management policy that has been used throughout the span of the project. The document covered the exploitation of public research data generated (and collected) within the project, the dissemination of the scientific results which are created by the project, as well as data ethics and security for sensitive data, and project guidelines for intellectual properties.

This document, an Open Research Data Pilot, has been periodically updated up to the end of the iNGENIOUS project, and contains all methods for the handling of project data.

6 REFERENCES

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